

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Stage art as an innovative didactic resource for the development of creativity in five-year-old children

El arte en la escena como recurso didáctico innovador para el desarrollo de la creatividad en niños de 5 años

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Abstract Stage art emerged as an innovative pedagogical strategy that allowed children to learn playfully while developing cognitive and emotional competencies. The study aimed to design a system of didactic activities to foster creativity in five-year-old children through theatrical practices. Using a descriptive, mixed-methods approach that incorporated empirical techniques such as observation and interviews, as well as theoretical methods including historical-logical, analytical-synthetic, and inductive-deductive reasoning, the study identified several difficulties among children, including stage fright, emotional insecurity, and limitations in bodily expression. It was also evident that teachers required training in innovative methodologies related to performing arts. The findings highlighted the importance of implementing flexible and contextually relevant didactic activities that can enrich teaching practices and promote integral development in early childhood, with the potential to be adapted to various educational contexts.

Keywords performing arts, body expression, social skills, early childhood education.

Resumen El arte en la escena se presentó como una estrategia pedagógica innovadora que permitió a los niños aprender de manera lúdica y desarrollar competencias cognitivas y emocionales. El estudio tuvo como objetivo diseñar un sistema de actividades didácticas para potenciar la creatividad en niños de 5 años mediante prácticas escénicas. Mediante un enfoque descriptivo y mixto, que incluyó métodos empíricos como la observación y la entrevista, así como métodos teóricos histórico-lógicos, analítico-sintéticos e inductivo-deductivos, se identificaron diversas dificultades en los niños, entre ellas el miedo escénico, la inseguridad emocional y las limitaciones en la expresión corporal. También se evidenció que los docentes requerían capacitación en metodologías innovadoras relacionadas con el arte escénico. Los resultados destacaron la relevancia de implementar actividades didácticas flexibles y contextualizadas, capaces de enriquecer la práctica pedagógica y favorecer el desarrollo integral en la primera infancia, y de adaptarse a distintos entornos educativos.

Palabras clave artes escénicas, expresión corporal, competencias sociales, educación infantil.

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Introduction

The historical antecedents of performing arts can be traced back to prehistoric rituals, and their evolution occurred in classical civilizations, such as the Greeks, which laid the foundations of theater and dance (Hosokawa et al., 2024). The Middle Ages saw the expansion of sacred theater and the development of other performing arts forms. At the same time, the Renaissance revitalized the genre with plays and the formalization of music and dance as artistic disciplines (Santos, 2015). Subsequently, performing arts continued to evolve throughout the centuries, reflecting social and cultural changes, until reaching the diverse and complex contemporary expressions.

Performing arts, understood as theatrical expression in early childhood education, play a fundamental role in children's holistic development, fostering creativity, emotional expression, and communication skills (Avellaneda, 2024). Through dramatization, children explore and express emotions, thoughts, and experiences, developing essential skills for their social and academic lives.

Several studies worldwide show that theater and play activities not only stimulate imagination but also strengthen socialization and children's identity (Saldaña et al., 2021). These practices allow children to experiment with real-life roles and situations, promoting their adaptation to different contexts and their positive interaction with others.

From a theoretical perspective, this study is based on Vygotsky's sociocultural approach, which emphasizes the importance of the social environment in children's learning. The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) allows children to progress in their learning through the guidance of adults or more experienced peers (Regader, 2015). In this sense, teaching performing arts in early childhood education constitutes a key space in which children, through social interaction, overcome cognitive barriers and develop new skills.

Performing arts are important in early childhood education because they can help children develop their creativity, their ability to express themselves, and a better understanding of the world around them, as well as develop skills such as observation, interpretation, and problem-solving (Botina, 2025). It can be an effective form of learning for children, as it allows them to explore different techniques and materials in a playful and fun way. It is also a therapeutic activity because it allows them to express their emotions and feelings healthily.

In Ecuador, the Early Childhood Education curriculum emphasizes the importance of providing comprehensive educational experiences that promote the cognitive, emotional, social, and physical development of children aged 3 to 5 (MINEDU, 2014). Within this context, art is considered a fundamental pillar of early childhood development, as it stimulates creativity and fosters skills such as communica-

tion, problem-solving, and empathy (Hosokawa et al., 2024). Furthermore, arts education in early childhood contributes to the development of critical thinking and strengthens socio-emotional competencies, which are essential at this formative stage.

Despite these guidelines, in many educational institutions across the country, performing arts education is not implemented in a structured and systematic manner (Claro, 2024). Although play and dramatization are recommended strategies in early childhood education, their application is often limited due to a lack of specific pedagogical planning and teacher training in this area.

According to Molina-Cevallos and Palma-Villavicencio (2022), human beings shape their personalities from the earliest years of life. Early childhood education strengthens this process, allowing individuals to develop their capacity to express their feelings and experience their emotions through body language, one of the primary forms of interaction with their environment. This study aims to provide teachers with an effective teaching tool that facilitates the implementation of artistic strategies in the classroom, promoting a more comprehensive and enriching approach to art education in early childhood.

In this context, it is urgent to create innovative activities that provide teachers with a clear and organized framework for effective implementation. These should include teaching guides, practical tools, and pedagogical approaches that promote the structured development of children's communicative, creative, and emotional skills. Furthermore, they should be adapted to the specific needs of the classroom so that five-year-olds can fully benefit from play-based and theatrical activities, thereby stimulating their creativity, emotional expression, and overall development.

Globally, early childhood education has been recognized as a fundamental stage in children's holistic development, in which art plays a key role in fostering creativity, emotional expression, and communication skills (Solas-Martínez et al., 2022). Art education promotes imagination and aesthetic sensitivity; it also contributes to the development of essential life skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration.

In this context, the performing arts, and drama in particular, have become established as an effective strategy for developing these skills in young children (Cornejo, 2019). However, in many educational institutions around the world, the teaching of performing arts lacks a structured methodological approach, which limits its impact on children's development.

In Ecuador, the Early Childhood Education curriculum emphasizes the importance of providing meaningful learning experiences that foster creativity and contribute to children's holistic development (MINEDUC, 2014). It recognizes that

play, exploration, and artistic activities are essential for stimulating children's emotional, social, and cognitive growth at this stage. Despite this recognition in educational regulations, the implementation of teaching strategies for performing arts remains deficient in many institutions across the country.

In this regard, the objective was to design a system of educational activities to develop creativity in 5-year-old children through performing arts. The lack of specific teacher training in artistic methodologies, along with the absence of adequate resources and structured planning, negatively impacts art education in early childhood (González, 2024). Consequently, children do not have access to dramatization experiences that would allow them to effectively develop their creativity, body expression, and emotional communication.

Methodology

This descriptive study aimed to observe, characterize, and detail the current state of performing arts in the classroom. According to Hernández et al. (2014), this type of research allowed for the specification of the properties and profiles of the analyzed phenomena without manipulating variables. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, integrating quantitative and qualitative methods. As Ishtiaq (2019) noted, this approach combined the collection of numerical data with the interpretation of qualitative information, enabling a broader understanding of educational issues. Specifically, the quantitative approach was used to systematize information on the frequency and methods of applying performing arts to five-year-old children, while the qualitative approach allowed for the interpretation of the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences of teachers and students.

The study population consisted of 72 children and 12 teachers from the 30 de Septiembre Educational Unit. Using purposive non-probability sampling, a sample of 25 five-year-old children and 5 teachers authorized to participate was selected. Scientific observation was conducted with the 25 children using a structured guide to assess their level of participation and the development of skills related to performing arts. Classroom activities were systematically recorded. Additionally, a structured interview was administered to the 5 teachers using a questionnaire to analyze their preparation, needs, and strengths in relation to the teaching and learning process of performing arts.

Results and discussion

Table 1 presents the results of the student performance evaluation in various theatrical activities. It includes indicators related to interest, ability to follow instructions, work efficiency, stage presence, and attention to detail. Each indicator allowed for the identification of general trends in group

behavior and the recognition of strengths and areas requiring reinforcement in the training process.

Table 1. Results of the evaluation of performance and behavior in theater activities

Indicator	Frequency (Percentage)		
	A lot	Bit	Nothing
Shows interest in theater activities	25 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
He has difficulty receiving and obeying instructions	3 (12%)	4 (16%)	18 (72%)
Perform work activities with agility	25 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
He finds it easy to perform on stage	21 (84%)	3 (12%)	1 (4%)
Demonstrates attention to stage work instructions	25 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

The results reflected a high level of motivation and interest among the 5-year-old children at the Unidad Educativa 30 de Septiembre school in performing arts activities. Regarding the first indicator, 100% of the students showed interest in theater, suggesting that these activities are engaging and can be an effective strategy for fostering learning. However, regarding the second indicator, 72% of the children had difficulty receiving and following instructions, while only 12% did so easily, and 16% experienced moderate difficulties. This highlights the need for teaching strategies that strengthen attention and comprehension of instructions during the process of teaching performing arts.

On the other hand, regarding the execution of activities with agility, 100% of the children demonstrated fluency and the ability to perform them successfully, indicating that they possess the necessary motor skills to participate in dramatizations. In relation to ease of acting on stage, 84% of the children performed without difficulty, while 12% showed insecurity and 4% experienced serious difficulties. This shows that, although most feel comfortable on stage, it is necessary to strengthen the confidence and expression of those students who still face barriers.

One hundred percent of the children paid attention to the instructions given on stage, suggesting that, despite initial difficulties in understanding them, they were able to follow them during the theater practice. Table 2 shows the responses of the teachers who participated in the study.

To perform the triangulation, the data obtained from the observation sheet were compared with the teacher's interview and the general conclusions of the research. The observations highlighted a strong interest in and ease with theatrical participation on the part of most of the children. These results were consistent with their high level of attention to

Table 2. Interviews were conducted with teachers

Subcategory	Ask	Answer
Teaching strategies	1. What is art on stage?	Teachers agree that performing arts is a set of artistic expressions that include theater, music, and dance, and also allows children to develop communication skills, body expression, and creativity.
	2. Which areas of the Basic Education curriculum facilitate the development of skills related to performing arts ?	Teachers primarily identified art education and language and literature, as these allow children to improve their communication skills, motor coordination, and self-confidence through dramatizations or songs.
	3. What are the teaching resources that contribute to the development of art on stage?	The teachers mention that the resources vary depending on the play or activity being developed. However, they usually use teaching aids appropriate to the theme (costumes, puppets, scenery) and a suitable physical space for practicing and performing the dramatizations.
Boost creativity	4. Have you done the staging and dramatization of small-format plays with your children ?	Some teachers have incorporated dramatizations into their classrooms, believing that these activities help children express themselves, foster their imagination, and strengthen their confidence in public speaking. They also mention that small-scale theater is a useful strategy for playfully reinforcing educational content.
	5. What benefits do you think dramatization offers in overcoming stage fright?	Although some teachers haven't given this aspect much thought, it's recognized that dramatization helps children become familiar with public speaking, reducing shyness and fear of making mistakes. Furthermore, it promotes emotional security and teamwork, contributing to the development of social and communication skills.
	6. Have you received training on methodologies for the development of performing arts in high school?	None of the teachers have received specific training in methodologies for developing performing arts. This highlights the need for training in didactic activity systems that promote the teaching of theater and other forms of artistic expression in early childhood education.
	7. How do you identify children who have developed linguistic-verbal intelligence?	Teachers have observed that children with high linguistic-verbal intelligence have been stimulated from an early age through storytelling and constant dialogue with their families and teachers. These children typically have an ease in communicating, expanding their vocabulary, and expressing themselves clearly and fluently.
	8. Do you believe that the application of a system of educational activities helps children to perform better in public?	All the teachers agree that implementing a system of didactic activities would foster the development of oral expression and children's self-confidence. By providing planned dramatization experiences, students can improve their confidence, acquire improvisation skills, and strengthen their emotional and social development.

instructions and commitment to the activities, demonstrating that theatrical techniques are attractive and effective for this age group.

The teacher mentioned that the dramatization had a positive impact on the children and helped them improve their learning. However, she acknowledged that she does not receive training in specific methodologies for developing performing arts, which could contribute to further improving the implementation of these activities.

It can be inferred that both instruments agree that performing arts activities create a conducive and effective learning environment. However, areas for improvement were identified, such as teacher training in theatrical techniques and additional support for students who have difficulty performing on stage.

It was found that all the children in the study learn easily when art and theater strategies are applied, which significantly impacts their academic performance. An interview was also conducted with the teacher to gather her opinions on art and theater for children. The methodological design for the research was established, focusing on the artistic disciplines that comprise performing arts, such as theater, dance, music, and visual arts.

Each of these disciplines contributes to children's holistic development through creative expression and social interaction. Theater, as a central tool of performing arts, allows children to experiment with different roles and situations, fostering their confidence and communication skills (Álvarez & Martín, 2016). Dance, for its part, improves motor coordination and body expression, fundamental aspects for the development of identity and self-confidence (Concha-Huarcaya et al., 2024). Music complements performance learning by promoting memory, auditory perception, and emotional sensitivity (Adu et al., 2024). Visual arts allow for a visual exploration of emotions and performance concepts, facilitating children's integration into the creative process (Onieva, 2011).

From a theoretical perspective, Gardner (1994) highlighted the relevance of multiple intelligences in child development, emphasizing that musical and bodily-kinesthetic intelligence are essential for artistic expression. Similarly, Molina-Cevallos and Palma-Villavicencio (2022) underscored the importance of theater as a didactic tool for developing communication and creativity in children. Vygotsky's sociocultural view emphasizes that learning occurs through interaction with others, reinforcing the value of performing arts as a means of social and cognitive development (Adu et al., 2024).

The combination of theater, dance, music, and visual arts in the teaching and learning process not only enriches the educational experience but also fosters values such as coope-

ration, empathy, and self-expression. The integration of these disciplines into the school curriculum should be promoted more strongly, as it offers a holistic and dynamic approach to child development. Furthermore, the incorporation of innovative methodologies, such as gamification and the use of technological tools, could further enhance the impact of the performing arts in education.

Throughout history, humankind has always been distinguished by its incredible capacity for creation, as evidenced by the remains found from prehistoric times, in which human beings already possessed artistic abilities that they used to understand their social and natural environment. These artistic expressions, linked to their beliefs and their interaction with the world around them, have been fundamental in the construction of human culture.

The performing arts encompass a range of artistic expressions presented to an audience on a stage or in a specific space, allowing individuals to channel their feelings and thoughts. According to Howe-Davies et al. (2023), children have the capacity to represent not only a story but also complex emotional states, such as fear or joy, and creativity, which facilitates their interaction with others and allows them to experience different perspectives. This ability to assume roles and express emotions through dramatization not only fosters communication but also strengthens empathy, as it allows them to understand the experiences and feelings of others.

The performing arts allow children to express and channel their thoughts and emotions through performances before an audience. By engaging in dramatization, children explore and communicate complex emotions, such as joy or fear, enabling them to interact more deeply with others (Álvarez, 2024). This ability to take on roles and express feelings not only improves communication but also strengthens empathy, as it allows them to put themselves in others' shoes, better understanding their experiences and emotions.

From a cognitive perspective, the performing arts allow for the transmission of knowledge specific to each stage of child development, facilitating the understanding of concepts and promoting memory and concentration. Emotionally, children release accumulated tension, while participation in theatrical activities fosters a positive self-concept and self-esteem, contributing to better social adaptation. Álvarez (2024) highlighted that these activities also promote autonomy, as children learn to make decisions within a group context, which fosters their emotional and social growth.

From a pedagogical perspective, Concha-Huarcaya et al. (2024) argued that performing arts not only strengthen children's affective development but also offer opportunities to improve their learning in other areas, such as language, reading comprehension, and motor skills. Through artistic activities, children develop their emotional intelligence and

their ability to learn playfully, making the educational process more meaningful and dynamic.

In this regard, performing arts have a holistic impact on children's development, as they not only strengthen their emotional well-being but also offer opportunities to improve other fundamental skills. Through artistic activities, children enrich their language and reading comprehension, which enhances their motor skills (Villaseñor & Gómez, 2021). By engaging in artistic processes, children develop their emotional intelligence and learn playfully, making the educational process a more meaningful and dynamic experience. This allows learning to be more engaging and effective, as it connects deeply with children's emotions and thinking.

Brown et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of fostering creativity in children. Teaching them to be creative not only enhances their abstract thinking and problem-solving skills but also has a positive impact on their academic performance by boosting their confidence and participation. According to Concha-Huarcaya et al. (2024), the arts are among the most effective resources for developing ideas and emotions in children, as they allow them to experiment, express themselves, and create freely and without restrictions, thus stimulating their creativity holistically.

Stimulating creativity in children not only fosters their ability to think abstractly and solve problems, but also has a positive impact on their academic performance by increasing their confidence and engagement. The arts are presented as one of the most effective tools for fostering this creativity, as they offer children a space in which they can experiment, express themselves, and create freely and without restrictions (William & Tasayco, 2003). This approach allows them to explore and develop ideas and emotions holistically, contributing to their cognitive, emotional, and social growth, and preparing them to face challenges in a more creative and flexible way.

Performing arts are a powerful tool in early childhood education, as they develop children's expressive, communicative, and emotional skills through dramatization and other forms of artistic expression. According to Álvarez and Martín (2016), children's theater fosters creativity and imagination, in addition to contributing to children's cognitive and emotional development.

Performing arts are proving to be a fundamental tool in early childhood education, offering a range of expressive, communicative, and emotional skills (Solas-Martínez et al., 2022). These types of activities foster deep learning that transcends the academic sphere and contributes significantly to children's cognitive and emotional development. By participating in these experiences, children interact with their environment more consciously, while also developing problem-solving and empathy skills.

Concha-Huarcaya et al. (2024) noted that participation in artistic activities allows children to explore different roles, which strengthens their self-confidence and empathy. Similarly, Adu et al. (2024) highlighted that creative drama is a valuable tool for cognitive, affective, social, and academic development.

From a theoretical perspective, Gardner (1994), with his theory of multiple intelligences, highlights the importance of art in child development, considering artistic expression to be an essential form of learning. Along these lines, López (2011) argued that dramatization is an effective teaching strategy for improving expression and communication in early childhood education.

Furthermore, performing arts allow for the development of problem-solving and critical thinking skills in children, providing them with the opportunity to confront diverse situations in a controlled and creative environment. Adu et al. (2024) emphasized that creative drama fosters reflection and analysis, helping children develop their decision-making abilities and autonomy.

Furthermore, integrating the performing arts with other educational disciplines, such as literature and emotional education, strengthens interdisciplinary learning. Álvarez and Martín (2016) argued that children's theater is a pedagogical strategy that stimulates reading comprehension and verbal expression, while also fostering empathy and cooperation among children.

Integrating performing arts with other educational disciplines reinforces children's interdisciplinary learning by allowing them to connect concepts and skills from different areas, work together, collaborate with each other, develop empathy, and create diverse artistic representations, which will help them strengthen their social and emotional relationships.

This reflects the importance of art in children's holistic development. Based on the premise of the previously cited authors, art not only serves as a form of aesthetic expression but also as a fundamental means for learning and identity formation (Santos, 2015). When children actively participate in artistic activities, such as theater, they are not only learning specific content but also developing essential emotional, social, and cognitive skills.

While Gardner (1994) focused on the impact of multiple intelligences on artistic expression, Santos (2015) emphasized the importance of experiential learning, and Concha-Huarcaya et al. (2024) highlighted social interaction as a key element in cognitive and emotional development. Together, these perspectives underscore the importance of children actively participating in performing arts programs, integrating different intelligences, constructing learning through experience, and benefiting from social interaction to enhance

their cognitive development.

From a more practical perspective, role-playing is a methodological strategy that fosters socialization and cooperation among children, helping them develop teamwork and problem-solving skills. Furthermore, studies such as those by Cornejo (2019) and Adu et al. (2024) have demonstrated that role-playing not only improves oral expression but also enhances critical thinking and empathy in children.

From the researcher's perspective, performing arts should be systematically incorporated into early childhood education, as they not only enhance creativity but also strengthen children's emotional and social development. Furthermore, their structured implementation in the classroom can have a positive impact on children's self-esteem, oral expression, and social interaction, promoting more dynamic and enriching learning experiences.

The characterization of the system of didactic activities is based, first and foremost, on its adaptability, since the content of the activities is designed according to the needs and characteristics of the students, allowing them to function effectively in the learning environment. This approach ensures that the information is accessible and meaningful, as it is structured around topics relevant and contextualized to their educational background.

Furthermore, the system is designed with flexibility in mind, allowing students to work with the activity content at

times the teacher deems most appropriate. This feature facilitates adapting the teaching and learning process to the group's pace, timing, and dynamics, without compromising the achievement of educational objectives.

Active participation is another fundamental aspect of the system, as students interact directly with the proposed content. This interaction fosters autonomy, decision-making, and personal growth by placing them at the center of their own learning process.

The innovative component is expressed in the incorporation of theater as an educational tool for the development of the performing arts. This novel methodology has the potential to transform traditional pedagogical practices, significantly contributing to the improvement of the teaching and learning process through creative, expressive, and meaningful experiences.

The set of activities (Table 3) presented below aims to enhance children's artistic expression and collaborative work through playful and creative activities. Each activity has been designed to stimulate imagination, strengthen communication skills, and promote group interaction using simple and accessible materials. Through these experiences, students are encouraged to explore new forms of representation, develop their narrative abilities, and build confidence in expressing themselves within an artistic environment, thus contributing to meaningful and enriching learning.

Table 3. Activities to stimulate imagination, strengthen communication skills, and promote group interaction

Activity #1. Shadow Theater - Animal Figures	
Aim	Encourage creativity and storytelling through the creation of shadow figures.
Methodology	Group work. The children will work in groups to create figures and develop a story.
Materials	Black cardstock, scissors, flashlights, skewers, images of animals or characters (printed or drawn).
Duration	40 minutes.
Procedure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The children, divided into groups, select characters or animals for their shadow (e.g., lion, clown, elephant, dragon). 2. They use cardboard to cut out the figures of the selected characters. 3. They glue the figures onto the sticks and place them in front of a light source (like a flashlight). 4. The groups create a short adventure story with their characters to represent it with shadows.
Assessment	The creativity of the stories, the coordination in group work, and the ability to communicate emotions through shadow play will be evaluated.
Activity #2. Body expression with music - Digital dance	
Aim	To promote emotional expression, rhythm and motor coordination through dance and technology.
Methodology	Individually and in pairs. The children will follow the instructions of an interactive video and then they will be able to dance in pairs.
Materials	Varied music (e.g., songs like "La Vaca Lola" or "El Baile del Pingüino"), tablet or computer, animation application or projection of dance videos.
Duration	30 minutes.

Procedure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The children will watch an interactive video of a simple dance (this could be a children's dance tutorial on YouTube or an app that allows them to follow the steps). Examples: "La Vaca Lola" (a video in which the children must imitate the cow's movements). 2. After watching the video, the children will dance individually following the movements, working on coordination and expression. 3. The children divide into pairs and perform a dance presentation together, demonstrating how to imitate their movements.
Assessment	The ability to keep up with the rhythm, emotional expression, and coordination as a couple will be assessed.
Activity #3. Interactive dramatization with projections	
Aim	Develop creativity, verbal expression and spatial coordination through interactive dramatizations.
Methodology	Group activity. The children will interact with projections while dramatizing the story.
Materials	Projector or screen, pre-recorded images or scenes from stories,
Duration	50 minutes.
Procedure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A scene from a story or tale is projected onto the wall, in which children can see the main characters in action. 2. After watching the projected scene, the children should interact with the characters, acting in their roles or creating new ones. 3. The projection can be alternated with live performances by the children, integrating changes in the story and allowing interaction with the projected characters. 4. The teacher will guide the activity, asking questions about the story and encouraging the children to think about how their characters would interact with the projected characters.
Assessment	Creativity in dramatization, the children's ability to interact with the projections, and the ability to follow the teacher's instructions will be evaluated.
Activity #4. Creating hand puppets with recycled material	
Aim	Develop creativity, fine motor skills and verbal expression through the creation of hand puppets.
Methodology	Group activity. The children will work in groups to create their puppets and then perform a short show.

Conclusions

The analysis revealed that performing arts played an essential role in children's holistic development, enhancing their creativity, socio-emotional skills, and problem-solving abilities. The assessment identified difficulties such as stage fright, emotional insecurity, and kinesthetic limitations, as well as the need for teacher training in performance methodologies. Based on these findings, a system of educational activities was designed that incorporated theatrical techniques to facilitate skill acquisition and effectively and sustainably strengthen children's comprehension and motor skills

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declares that she has no conflict of interest.

Author contributions

Carmen M. Zambrano: Conceptualization, formal analysis, research, methodology, writing the original draft, Writing, review and editing.

Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Statement on the use of AI

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